

Superoxide ion induced diastereoselective synthesis of α -cyanocinnamates

Raghvendra Singh Raghuvanshi* and Ajay Kumar Shukla

Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science, Udai Pratap Autonomous College, Varanasi-221 002, Uttar Pradesh, India

E-mail : rsr_itbhu@rediffmail.com

Manuscript received 13 September 2011, revised 26 September 2012, accepted 13 February 2013

Abstract : Knoevenagel condensation of ethyl cyanoacetate with aromatic aldehydes using superoxide ion results (*E*)-ethyl α -cyanocinnamates in good to excellent yield under mild reaction conditions, at room temperature.

Keywords : Knoevenagel condensation, superoxide, ethyl cyanocinnamate.

Introduction

The Knoevenagel condensation is one of the most important carbon-carbon bond forming reactions available, because the alkenes synthesized are very useful intermediates in organic synthesis¹. Ethyl α -cyanocinnamates are a class of important organic compounds used in photosensitive composition², intermediate of plant growth regulators³, ultraviolet filters composition⁴, dye for synthetic polymer fibers⁵, anionic polymerization⁶ and showed fungicidal, herbicidal and insecticidal activity⁷. Preparation of ethyl α -cyanocinnamates was usually completed via Knoevenagel condensation between ethyl cyanoacetate and various aromatic aldehydes. This reaction usually catalyzed by alkali metal hydroxides and amines¹. In recent years the use of I_2 - K_2CO_3 ⁸, K_3PO_4 ⁹, KF - Al_2O_3 ¹⁰, cetyltriethylammonium bromide/ H_2O ¹¹, diammonium hydrogen phosphate¹², ionic liquid/functionalized silica gel¹³, ionic liquid/SBA-15¹⁴, fluorapatite¹⁵, natural phosphate/ $KF/NaNO_2$ ¹⁶, calcite/fluoride¹⁷, polystyrene/piperazine¹⁸, basic ionic liquid¹⁹, MgO/ZrO_2 ²⁰, cyclic guanidinium lactate ionic liquid²¹, 2-hydroxyethylammonium acetate²² and imidazolium-based phosphinite ionic liquid²³ have been reported. Some method suffers from low yields, long reaction times and harsh conditions.

Superoxide ion (\bar{O}_2^*) easily formed in the body, has been known as toxic species to cause a serious damage to living organisms²⁴. Recently, much effort has been made not only its biological toxicity but also on its application in organic synthesis²⁵⁻³¹. Keeping these facts in view

herein, we report a mild and efficient condensation between ethyl cyanoacetate and various aldehydes using *in situ* generated superoxide ion in dry DMF, at room temperature (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

In the present course of reaction, \bar{O}_2^* generated *in situ* by the phase transfer reaction of KO_2 and 18-crown-6 in DMF at room temperature^{32,33} and subsequently allowed to react with aromatic aldehydes in the presence of ethyl cyanoacetate. As an outcome, ethyl cyanoacetate readily condenses with aromatic aldehydes to afford ethyl α -cyanocinnamates in good to excellent yield (Table 1). Electron donating groups such as $-NH_2$, $-OCH_3$, $-OH$, $-CH_3$ in the aromatic ring do not retard the condensation under these conditions.

A molar ratio of 1 : 1 : 1 for substrate **1** : ethyl cyanoacetate : KO_2 was employed for achieving the reaction. Each reaction was monitored by TLC for its comple-

Entry	Aldehyde	Ethyl cyanoacetate	Product	Yield (%)
1.				84
2.				81
3.				82
4.				80
5.				85
6.				88
7.				79
8.				75
9.				78
10.				82

tion. The products were fully identified by their physical and spectral data, which were in full agreement with the values described in literature^{23,34-37}.

Experimental

Potassium superoxide, 18-crown-6 and ethyl cyanoacetate were Aldrich products and were used as received. Dry DMF of Aldrich, was stored over molecular sieves (4 Å) prior to use. Melting points were mea-

sured in open capillaries and are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on a JASCO FT/IR-5300 spectrophotometer, NMR spectra were run on a JEOL AL300 FT-NMR and chemical shift are expressed as δ (ppm), using TMS as internal reference.

General procedure for the reaction of in situ generated superoxide ion with ethyl cyanoacetate and aromatic aldehyde :

In a three necked round bottom flask provided with a magnetic stirrer, N_2 inlet, Leibig condenser and dropping funnel, protected by calcium chloride drying tube was added dimethylformamide (25 ml). Potassium superoxide (0.68 g; 0.0096 mol) and 18-crown-6 ether (1.27 g; 0.0048 mol) were weighed under nitrogen atmosphere using atmobag and were transferred into the flask. To the stirred reaction mixture, were added ethyl cyanoacetate (0.0096 mol) followed by dropwise addition of aromatic aldehyde (0.0096 mol). Nitrogen was bubbled continuously and reaction mixture was stirred over magnetic stirrer for 3–5 h at room temperature until the starting material was consumed as indicated by TLC. The mixture was successively treated with saturated aqueous sodium chloride (20 ml) and sodium bicarbonate (20 ml) solution and then extracted with dichloromethane (3 \times 20 ml). The combined organic layer was dried over Na_2SO_4 (anhyd.), filtered and evaporated to furnish a residue, which was recrystallized from 95% ethanol and identified by 1H NMR and IR spectroscopy.

(*E*)-Ethyl-2-cyano-3-phenylacrylate (**3a**) : m.p. 49–50 °C (lit.²³ 49 °C); IR (KBr) : ν 2218, 1725, 1599 cm^{-1} ; 1H NMR (300 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : δ 1.4 (3H, t, J 7.2 Hz), 4.4 (2H, q, J 7.2 Hz), 7.4–7.6 (3H, m), 8.0 (2H, m), 8.3 (1H, s).

(*E*)-Ethyl-3-(4-chlorophenyl)-2-cyanoacrylate (**3b**) : m.p. 93 °C (lit.²³ 92–94 °C); IR (KBr) : ν 2226, 1725, 1618 cm^{-1} ; 1H NMR (300 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : δ 1.5 (3H, t, J 7.3 Hz), 4.5 (2H, q, J 7.3 Hz), 7.7–7.9 (4H, m), 8.1 (1H, s).

(*E*)-Ethyl-2-cyano-3-(4-methylphenyl)-acrylate (**3c**) : m.p. 91 °C (lit.³⁴ 90 °C); IR (KBr) : ν 2218, 1727, 1599 cm^{-1} ; 1H NMR (300 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : δ 1.4 (3H, t, J 7.1 Hz), 2.4 (3H, s), 4.4 (2H, q, J 7.1 Hz), 7.3 (2H, d, J 8.4 Hz), 7.9 (2H, d, J 8.4 Hz), 8.2 (1H, s).

(*E*)-Ethyl-2-cyano-3-(4-methoxyphenyl)-acrylate (**3d**) : m.p. 78 °C (lit.³⁵ 79 °C); IR (KBr) : ν 2215, 1719, 1588 cm^{-1} ; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 1.4 (3H, t, J 7.4 Hz), 3.9 (3H, s), 4.4 (2H, q, J 7.2 Hz), 7.1 (2H, d, J 8.4 Hz), 8.1 (2H, d, J 8.4 Hz), 8.2 (1H, s).

(*E*)-Ethyl-2-cyano-3-(3-nitrophenyl)-acrylate (**3e**) : m.p. 135–136 °C (lit.³⁶ 134–136 °C); IR (KBr) : ν 2242, 1719, 1612, 1520 cm^{-1} ; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 1.4 (3H, t, J 7.2 Hz), 4.4 (2H, q, J 7.2 Hz), 7.7 (1H, m), 8.3 (1H, s), 8.4–8.7 (3H, m).

(*E*)-Ethyl-2-cyano-3-(4-nitrophenyl)-acrylate (**3f**) : m.p. 170 °C (lit.³⁶ 170–171 °C); IR (KBr) : ν 3280, 3018, 2400, 2332, 1731, 1665, 1533, 1266, 760 cm^{-1} ; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 1.4 (3H, t, J 7.0 Hz), 4.4 (2H, q, J 7.0 Hz), 8.1–8.3 (4H, m), 8.4 (1H, s).

(*E*)-Ethyl-3-(4-aminophenyl)-2-cyanoacrylate (**3g**) : m.p. 165 °C (lit.³⁶ 164–165 °C); IR (KBr) : ν 3454, 3350, 2223, 1690, 1580, 1452 cm^{-1} ; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 1.3 (3H, t, J 7.1 Hz), 4.3 (2H, q, J 7.2 Hz), 6.7 (2H, d, J 8.8 Hz), 7.8 (2H, d, J 8.8 Hz), 8.0 (1H, s).

(*E*)-Ethyl-2-cyano-3-(4-hydroxyphenyl)-acrylate (**3h**) : m.p. 169–170 °C (lit.³⁶ 170–171 °C); IR (KBr) : ν 3292, 2234, 1718, 1591 cm^{-1} ; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 1.4 (3H, t, J 7.1 Hz), 4.4 (2H, q, J 7.1 Hz), 6.6 (1H, br. s), 7.0 (2H, d, J 8.7 Hz), 7.9 (2H, d, J 8.7 Hz), 8.2 (1H, s).

(*E*)-Ethyl-2-cyano-3-(3-methoxy-4-hydroxyphenyl)-acrylate (**3i**) : m.p. 108 °C (lit.³⁵ 107–108 °C); IR (KBr) : ν 3380, 2230, 1705, 1576 cm^{-1} ; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 1.4 (3H, t, J 7.1 Hz), 3.9 (3H, s), 4.4 (2H, q, J 7.1 Hz), 6.2 (1H, br. s), 7.0 (1H, d, J 8.3 Hz), 7.4 (1H, d, J 8.3 Hz), 7.9 (1H, s), 8.2 (1H, s).

(*E*)-Ethyl-2-cyano-3-(2-methylphenyl)-acrylate (**3j**) : m.p. 52–53 °C (lit.³⁷ 52–54 °C); IR (KBr) : ν 2225, 1735, 1594 cm^{-1} ; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) : δ 1.4 (3H, t, J 7.3 Hz), 2.4 (3H, s), 4.4 (2H, q, J 7.3 Hz), 7.2–7.4 (2H, m), 7.8–8.0 (2H, m), 8.2 (1H, s).

Conclusion

In summary, we have demonstrated a mild and efficient procedure for the preparation of (*E*)-ethyl α -cyanocinnamates by employing *in situ* generated superoxide ion.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to University Grants Commission, New Delhi for financial support.

References

- G. Jones, *Org. React.*, 1967, **15**, 204.
- H. Teichmann and W. Thierfelder, Ger. Patent (East), 1978, **129**, 959.
- H. Oba, T. Murayama and S. Otsuka, US Patent, 1998, **4184**, 871.
- B. A. Farbenfabriken, Ger. Patent, 1960, **1087**, 908.
- A. T. Peters, M. S. Wild and S. J. Otsuka, *Soc. Dyes Colour*, 1994, **93**, 347.
- S. M. Lai, C. P. Ng, R. Martin-Aranda and K. L. Yong, *Mesopor. Mater.*, 2003, **66**, 239.
- I. R. Pitta, A. Boucherle and D. Pillon, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.-Chim. Ther.*, 1974, **9**, 347.
- Y. Ren and C. Cai, *Synth. Commun.*, 2007, **37**, 2209.
- Y. Li, *J. Chem. Res.*, 2000, 524.
- S. Wang, J. Li, W. Yang and T. Li, *Ultrason. Sonochem.*, 2002, **9**, 159.
- S. Wang, Z. Ren, W. Cao and W. Tong, *Synth. Commun.*, 2001, **31**, 673.
- B. Saeed, B. Morteza, H. Shohreh and S. Peyman, *Synth. Commun.*, 2006, **36**, 2549.
- G. Lai, J. Peng, J. Li, H. Qiu, J. Jiang, K. Jiang and Y. Shen, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2006, **47**, 6951.
- Y. Liu, J. Peng, S. Zhai, J. Li, J. Mao, M. Li, H. Qiu and G. Lai, *Eur. J. Inorg. Chem.*, 2006, 2947.
- S. Sebti, R. Nazih, R. Tahir, L. Salhi and A. Saber, *Appl. Catal. (A)*, 2000, **197**, 187.
- S. Sebti, A. Smahi and A. Solhy, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2002, **43**, 1813.
- S. Wade and S. Suzuki, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2003, **44**, 399.
- G. Yang, Z. Chen, G. Xu and X. Nie, *Catal. Commun.*, 2004, **5**, 75.
- B. C. Ranu and R. Jana, *Eur. J. Org. Chem.*, 2006, 3767.
- M. B. Gawande and R. V. Jayaram, *Catal. Commun.*, 2006, **7**, 931.
- X. Xin, X. Guo, H. Duan, Y. Lin and H. Sun, *Catal. Commun.*, 2007, **8**, 115.
- Z. Zhou, J. Yuan and R. Yang, *Synth. Commun.*, 2009, **39**, 2001.
- H. Valizadeh and H. Gholipour, *Synth. Commun.*, 2010, **40**, 1477.
- B. Halliwell and J. M. C. Gutteridge, "Free Radicals in Biology and Medicine", Clarendon Press, Oxford, 1989, p. 136.

25. R. S. Raghuvanshi and K. N. Singh, *Synth. Commun.*, 2006, **36**, 3075.
26. R. S. Raghuvanshi and K. N. Singh, *Synth. Commun.*, 2007, **37**, 1371.
27. R. S. Raghuvanshi and K. N. Singh, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 2008, **47**, 1735.
28. R. S. Raghuvanshi and K. N. Singh, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 2009, **48**, 1161.
29. Y.-J. Chen and J.-Y. Shen, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2005, **46**, 4205.
30. N. Shankaraiah and L. S. Santos, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2009, **50**, 520.
31. I. M. AlNashef, M. A. Hashim, F. S. Mjalli, M. Q. A. Ali and M. Hayyan, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2010, **51**, 1976.
32. M. J. Gibian, D. T. Sawyer, T. Ungermann, R. Tangpoonphalvivat and M. M. Morrison, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **101**, 640.
33. K. N. Singh, R. S. Raghuvanshi and M. Singh, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 2007, **46**, 829.
34. N. Iranpoor, H. Firouzabadi and R. Azadi, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2006, **47**, 5531.
35. F. D. Popp, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1960, **25**, 646.
36. J.-T. Li, T.-S. Li, L.-J. Li and X. Cheng, *Ultrason. Sonochem.*, 1999, **6**, 199.
37. T.-S. Jin, J.-J. Guo, H.-M. Liu and T.-S. Liu, *Synth. Commun.*, 2003, **33**, 783.